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Unveiling the Triple Transformation in Supply Chain Management: A BERT-Based Topic Modeling and Fuzzy C-Means Clustering Approach

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ABSTRACT

The altering dynamics of supply chain management are increasingly influenced by the progressive adaptation of digital, green, and social transformations, named under the "triple transformation". This study aims to thoroughly examine the existing academic literature regarding the triple transformation in supply chains through the application of modern natural language processing and clustering methodologies. A corpus of 5586, 5575, and 7672 peer-reviewed articles is obtained for social, digital, and green transformation respectively. Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformers (BERT)-based topic modeling is used to reveal underlying theme structures, facilitating semantically rich embedding and contextualized topic extraction. Subsequently, the identified topics are categorized utilizing the fuzzy c-means clustering technique to examine the intersections and differences across research themes pertaining to digitalization, sustainability, and social responsibility in supply chains. The results provide a detailed overview of the research gap, emphasizing fundamental topics, interdisciplinary trends, and upcoming issues.

KEYWORDS - Bert model, digital transformation, fuzzy c-means, green transformation, social transformation, triple transformation

1. Introduction

The twin transformation is a strategy that integrates green and digital transformations to create more sustainable systems. This methodology proposes that leveraging digital technologies enables enterprises to enhance resource efficiency, implement circular practices, and eventually promote better sustainability [1]. The transformation from twin to triple transformation introduces a vital third component: social and behavioral transformation. This necessitates a transformation in attitudes and conduct, wherein individuals embrace sustainability and assume accountability for their activities, personal welfare, and the welfare of their communities and the environment [2]. Social transformation encompasses a broad spectrum of elements, including education and awareness, active community participation, the promotion of sustainable lifestyles, and the establishment of transparent and accountable governance [2]. A triple transformation paradigm would facilitate the establishment of a systemic approach by recognizing that tackling a single issue in isolation may produce limited outcomes, as the underlying causes of numerous problems are interconnected. The triple transformation would concurrently promote: i) enhanced productivity, innovation, and digital inclusiveness; ii) a sustainable economy; and iii) improved social well-being and cohesiveness through participatory and lawful

decision-making procedures [3]. To enhance partnerships and achieve the triple transformation—green, digital, and social—the new multidimensional partnership seeks to encourage investment and collaboration in areas such as clean energy, essential raw materials, and sustainable supply chains. It will also cover broader topics including human rights, the rule of law, good governance, and gender equality [3].

The complexities of globalization and the contemporary economic landscape have made supply chains increasingly intricate, complicating their construction, organization, and interaction. Increasing environmental and societal issues necessitate a fundamental transition from firm-specific to supply chain-focused attention, aligning organizational and sustainability objectives [4]. The term "triple transformation," while not yet firmly established in the literature as a cohesive idea, can characterize the concurrent implementation of digital, green, and social transformation paths in supply chain management, each of which have been thoroughly examined. The concept of triple transformation in supply chain management pertains to the simultaneous and interconnected implementation of digital, green, and social transformation techniques to improve operational resilience, sustainability, and ethical accountability. This comprehensive approach is increasingly acknowledged as vital for synchronizing supply chain processes with the changing requirements of technology advancement, environmental responsibility, and social justice. Although the term "triple transformation" is still emerging in academic literature, it offers a comprehensive framework to evaluate how supply chains can evolve in response to the multi-dimensional issues of the 21st century. As a nexus of technological advancement, environmental responsibility, and social equity, supply chain management offers an ideal context to examine how these three transformation paths intersect in practice.

Despite a growing body of literature addressing these themes individually, a comprehensive synthesis of their convergence in the context of supply chain management is still lacking. This gap limits our understanding of how these transformation paths interact, overlap, or diverge in shaping the future of supply chains. To address this, the present study aims to systematically examine the academic discourse surrounding each transformation dimension—digital, green, and social—within the domain of supply chain management. Leveraging advanced natural language processing techniques, specifically Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformers (BERT)-based topic modeling and fuzzy c-means clustering, this research categorizes and analyzes peer-reviewed articles sourced from Scopus database. The goal is to uncover the thematic structure of the literature and provide an integrated view of emerging research areas, existing gaps, and interdisciplinary trends that define the trajectory of triple transformation in supply chains. The following section explores existing literature across these three transformation dimensions to identify key research themes and intersections in the context of supply chain management.

2.Literature Review

2.1.Digital transformation in supply chain management

Digital transformation denotes a holistic change in business strategies, management frameworks, and operations through the integration of digital technologies. It involves the digitalization of operations, the establishment of extensive supply chain linkages, and the utilization of the internet across numerous business facets. This change will result in enhanced products and services, increased operational efficiency, cost savings, and a competitive edge in the market [5], [6]. Given the extensive scope of existing research, this section presents a selective overview of relevant studies that exemplify current advancements in digital, blockchain-based, and IoT-enabled transformations within supply chains.

Spanaki et al. [1] underscored the significance of data-driven technologies—such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and big data analytics—in transforming operations and supply chain management. Despite comprehensive research efforts, a significant gap remains between theoretical constructs and their practical use. This disconnection highlights the necessity for more research to align

academic insights with practical applications and advocates for a more holistic and integrated methodology for comprehending and implementing data-driven digital transformation strategies in operations and supply chain management. Xi et al. [7] examined the motivations behind organizations' adherence to their customers and suppliers in the adoption of digital transformation initiatives. Textual analysis of quarterly conference calls revealed that organizations implement digital transformation plans in response to their suppliers and consumers, suggesting that digital transformation propagates across the supply chain. Patel et al. [8] explored the capacity of blockchain technology to transform the jewelry supply chain by improving trust, transparency, and efficiency. They constructed a blockchain network utilizing Ethereum, specifically designed to meet the industry's requirements. Imran Alam et al. [9] intended to enhance transparency, security, and efficiency in the coal supply chain management process through the use of a blockchain-based system. They examined the constraints of the current coal supply chain systems and highlighted the promise of blockchain technology. Bahrampour et al. [10] demonstrated the implementation of vendor-managed inventory (VMI) in business-to-business and business-to-consumer relationships within a multi-echelon supply chain, utilizing innovative Industry 4.0 technologies such as the IoT and smart contracts. The execution of the VMI plan necessitates precise and prompt data, including inventory levels, point-of-sale information, and perhaps data on returned products; therefore, they advocated for the utilization of IoT technology as a means to obtain timely data. Additionally, they suggested a smart contract to automate the implementation and execution of VMI norms and standards, hence enhancing operational clarity and fostering confidence among supply chain participants. Nozari et al. [11] proposed a mathematical model for a dual-channel supply chain network under uncertainty, integrating IoT. The objective is to enhance overall profit by optimizing demand allocation, pricing strategies, distribution center placements, and IoT integration through artificial intelligence algorithms.

2.2 Green transformation in supply chain management

The idea of green transformation underscores environmental sustainability and ecological equilibrium, asserting that industrial and economic activity must align harmoniously with nature. The green transformation is an expansive concept encompassing goals such as environmental sustainability, natural resource conservation, climate change mitigation, and energy efficiency, referring to the advancement of the economy or society in an ecologically sustainable manner [12]. The concept of green transformation in supply chain management highlights the incorporation of environmentally sustainable methods throughout all phases of the supply chain – encompassing sourcing, production, distribution, and reverse logistics. It seeks to reduce the environmental impact of supply chain activities through tactics including carbon emissions reduction, energy efficiency, waste minimization, circular resource flows, and the utilization of sustainable materials [13]. This section emphasizes specific academic research about the green transformation of supply chains in diverse contexts. Although the literature on this subject is extensive, the subsequent studies have been selected to exemplify various dimensions.

Junejo et al. [14] examined the influence of green supply chain management on the sustainable performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Pakistan. Their research emphasizes the intermediary functions of green knowledge dissemination, green innovation, and big data-driven supply chains. The findings underscore the necessity of integrating environmental practices into SME operations to address resource limitations and regulatory obstacles in developing economies. Pan et al. [15] investigated the influence of ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) practices on the advancement of green investment in Chinese supply chains. The research demonstrated that corporate green investment practices display peer influences across supply chain partners, propelled by institutional pressure and information dissemination. This study offers significant insights into how ESG mechanisms promote cooperative environmental governance among companies. Mao et al. [16] quantified the risk of carbon price volatility using statistical data from China's carbon trading market, employed prospect theory to illustrate the investment risk preferences of enterprises, and utilized the evolutionary game model to analyze the dynamic evolution of the two-stages sustainable supply chain

system. The model illustrates that government laws and fluctuations in carbon pricing substantially affect strategic choices, with suppliers exhibiting greater sensitivity to penalties and manufacturers showing a stronger propensity for green innovation. Labaran and Masood [17] concentrated on sustainability and supply chain challenges within Africa's renewable energy sector. Utilizing qualitative data from energy companies and regulatory bodies, they suggested solutions grounded in green supply chain management and Industry 4.0 technologies, including IoT, blockchain, and big data analytics. Their research highlights the significance of digital tools in addressing sector-specific environmental and logistical issues.

2.3. Social transformation in supply chain management

Kohlgrüber et al. [18] contend that innovation processes should be perceived as social innovation processes, encompassing co-creation with employees, users, and communities. This perspective emphasizes the necessity of including human-centric design, inclusive employment policies, and cross-sector collaboration in the deployment of digital and sustainable technologies within supply chain environments. Social transformation encompasses not just the enhancement of labor conditions and the assurance of ethical sourcing but also the reorganization of work practices, stakeholder engagement, and organizational learning that accompany technical advancements. While digital and green innovations are crucial to the evolution of contemporary supply chains, researchers assert that technological progress must be complemented by non-technological, social factors to realize systemic transformation. This section emphasizes specific academic research about the social transformation of supply chains in diverse contexts.

Recent studies have increasingly emphasized the human-centric transformation of supply chains under the developing paradigm of supply chain. Zaid et al. [19] examined the impact of the industry 5.0 paradigm on supply chain research and improves the field of supply chain management by emphasizing the possibilities for human-centered supply chain management. They clarified how Industry 5.0 facilitates supply chain evaluation and enhancement, assisting companies in managing disruptions while maintaining competitiveness and profitability. Their approach incorporates Maslow's hierarchy of needs to assess how supply chains can more effectively serve workers, stakeholders, and end-users. Gowsalya and Kuriyakose [20] enhanced this discussion by examining the adaptation of Markov-based AI models to meet human and ecological concerns inside supply chain networks. Their research underscores the necessity for ethical considerations and awareness of employment dynamics amidst increasing automation. Villar et al. [21] presented a systematic review of supply chain 5.0 literature, highlighting human centricity, sustainability, and resilience as the three fundamental pillars of the fifth industrial revolution. The bibliometric analysis indicates an increasing interest in technologies that facilitate human-machine interaction, personalization, and worker empowerment.

Transparency and ethical sourcing are widely acknowledged as essential components of responsible and sustainable supply chain management. Trung et al. [22] proposed a blockchain-based framework for the handicraft sector to improve ethical sourcing by ensuring transparency and traceability from makers to end consumers. Their platform incorporates blockchain, smart contracts, non-fungible tokens (NFTs), and the interplanetary file system (IPFS) to authenticate product origins and guarantee equitable practices. Tandon et al. [23] emphasized that in the fashion industry, ethical sourcing exceeds formal standards and involves the moral agency of employees confronting ethical challenges at many decision-making levels. Their longitudinal study highlights the importance of personal ethical accountability and the necessity for organizational settings that foster ethical behavior across the supply chain. Cromwell et al. [24] highlighted the significance of digital traceability technologies, such as blockchain, IoT, and RFID, in improving transparency and accountability across global fish supply chains. Li et al. [25] investigated two practices for the transparency of the retailer's information acquisition state: non-transparency and complete transparency. By including a manufacturer's information belief adjustment technique, their study covers a retailer's acquisition and ex-post sharing of information (i.e., how to share obtained information) under the two transparency modes.

The enforcement of labor rights and the improvement of working conditions remain major concerns in global supply chains, particularly in labor-intensive businesses that operate in developing economies. Recent academic contributions have addressed these concerns from a variety of perspectives. Hiessl [26] examined the EU's legislative efforts, particularly the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive, and emphasized its potential to shift from voluntary corporate social responsibility practices to binding labor rights enforcement throughout global value chains. Islam and Van Staden [27] examined how labor rights activism and political environment influence business disclosures regarding contemporary slavery audits, demonstrating that stakeholder pressure is crucial in improving corporate transparency. Bag and Dhamija [28] performed a comprehensive assessment that focuses on the impact of institutional governance and business ethics in promoting decent work standards. They advocated for integrated measures to eliminate forced labor, enforce safety standards, and ensure gender parity in global supply chains. SoundArarajan et al. [29] provided a new perspective on the challenge of improving working conditions inside global supply chains by conducting a comprehensive assessment that incorporates insights from several social science fields. They began by identifying characteristics at numerous levels—supply chain, workplace, individual, and institutional—that lead to poor working conditions, and then investigated how these elements, in specific combinations, contribute to poor working conditions in various sample archetypes of global supply systems.

These studies show that the digital, green, and social transformations of supply chains are all interconnected and complex. While each dimension presents unique problems and strategic implications, their integration is increasingly seen as critical to building resilient, sustainable, and ethically aligned supply chain systems. Despite tremendous academic achievement in individual disciplines, the confluence of three transformations—also known as the "triple transformation"—remains comparatively unexplored in a cohesive and comparative context.

3. Methodology

The proposed methodology begins with document collection and preprocessing, proceeds through the generation of dense sentence embeddings and BERT topic-based topic modeling, employs Xie–Beni and Silhouette indices for cluster validation and optimal cluster selection, and then applies fuzzy c-means clustering for thematic profiling before culminating in result interpretation as seen in Fig. 1. Traditional machine learning models offer interpretability and demand fewer computational resources, rendering them appropriate for situations with constrained data, whereas BERT utilizes profound contextual comprehension to improve sentiment classification and its prominence and efficacy across various natural language processing (NLP) tasks [30].

Distinct search queries are employed individually to collect the peer-reviewed corpora for each aforementioned transformations. The search query for social is specified as “(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("supply chain") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("social transformation") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("labor rights") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("ethical sourcing") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("transparency") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("human centric") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("working condition")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))”. Subsequently, the green transformation is contemplated, and the search query is established as “(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("supply chain") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("green transformation") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (green)) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))”. The final search query for digital transformation is formulated as “(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("supply chain") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("digital transformation") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (blockchain) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("internet of things")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))”. The applications were executed on a machine featuring an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-9750H CPU operating at 2.60GHz, 8 GB of RAM (2400 MHz), and a 4 GB GPU.

Fig. 1. Methodology flowchart

The analysis commences with the parsing of an individual raw text file. Paragraph borders have been delineated. This produces a refined list of abstracts that forms the domain-specific corpus for all ensuing NLP tasks. Subsequently, each abstract undergoes preprocessing to remove extraneous tokens using a built regular expression, therefore ensuring that the lexical space provided to downstream models is devoid of irrelevant noise. The subsequent phase involves the application of sentence embedding. Each cleaned abstract is encoded using the sentence transformer model all-MiniLM-L6-v2 to achieve fixed-length semantic representations. The model transforms each document into a 384-dimensional dense embedding vector that maintains contextual semantics appropriate for distance-based learning. Due to the hindrance of grouping by high-dimensional embedding, the vectors are projected into a five-dimensional manifold using UMAP (Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection). This approach maintains local semantic topology while significantly reducing dimensionality.

BERT is a transformer model introduced by Devlin et al. [31] in 2018. BERT consists of a series of encoder blocks that utilize the attention mechanism to enhance the understanding of linguistic context. The input text is segmented into tokens, and each token is converted into a vector in BERT's output. BERT is concurrently trained using the Masked Language Model (MLM) for language creation and the Next Sentence Prediction (NSP) task [32]. In accordance with, the diminished vectors are directly input into BERTopic, which integrates hierarchical density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise

(HDBSCAN) clustering, class-based Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) enhancement in the proposed study. A topic designated as an outlier, labeled -1 , is generated by BERTopic but is excluded from subsequent analysis to retain only significant subjects. The collection of probability vectors is organized into a matrix. Each row signifies a document, whereas each column denotes a viable topic. This matrix serves as the quantitative foundation for fuzzy clustering and validity assessments. For interpretability, the BERTopic library generates topic labels by routinely extracting four-word, high-salience labels for each topic, offering succinct semantic descriptors utilized in subsequent qualitative interpretation. For each candidate c , two complimentary indices are calculated:

- The Xie–Beni index indicates that lower values correspond to dense clusters with significant pairwise separation [33].
- The Silhouette Coefficient, calculated using hard labels ($\text{argmax}(U)$) and cosine distance, indicates superior cohesion and separation with larger values [34].

Results are aggregated in a metrics data frame and illustrated to visualize trade-offs across c . The highest cluster count of the Silhouette index and the Xie–Beni index is selected as the default optimal c . Hard cluster labels obtained from U are added to the original probability data frame. For each cluster k , the mean topic-probability vector is calculated; the five topics with the highest probabilities and their averages are identified as the dominating themes of that cluster. The document nearest to centroid v_k (in Euclidean distance) is selected, and its five principal subjects are provided. All summaries have been combined. Ultimately, quantitative outputs (predominant topics, representative documents, validity indices) are qualitatively analyzed to elucidate the interconnections among social, environmental, and digital developments. This synthesis constitutes the core results part of any resultant publication. Flowchart for the applied methodology is given in Fig.1.

The clustering phase of this study employs the fuzzy c -means algorithm, while cluster validity is assessed with the Xie–Beni index and the cosine-based Silhouette coefficient. In fuzzy c -means the data set $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ is partitioned into c clusters ($2 \leq c \leq N$) by minimizing the objective (Eq. 1) [35]:

$$J_m(U, V) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^c u_{ki}^m \|x_i - u_k\|^2 \quad (1)$$

where $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_c\}$ denotes the set of centroids, $U = [u_{ki}]$ the membership matrix, and $m > 1$ the fuzzifier (fixed to $m = 2$ in all experiments). Memberships satisfy $\sum_{k=1}^c u_{ik} = 1$ and $0 < u_{ik} < 1$ for every object x_i . The algorithm iteratively updates (Eq. 2, 3):

$$u_k^{(t+1)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N u_{ki}^m x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N u_{ki}^m}, \quad (2)$$

$$u_{ki}^{(t+1)} = \frac{\|x_i - v_k^{(t+1)}\|^{-\frac{2}{m-1}}}{\sum_{r=1}^c \|x_i - v_r^{(t+1)}\|^{-\frac{2}{m-1}}} \quad (3)$$

Iterations cease when $\max_{k,i} |u_{ki}^{(t+1)} - u_{ki}^{(t)}| < \varepsilon$ or a preset iteration limit is reached.

Cluster quality is first quantified by the Xie–Beni index (Eq. 4) [33]:

$$XB(U, V) = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^c \sum_{i=1}^N u_{ki}^2 \|x_i - v_k\|^2}{N \min_{p \neq q} \|v_p - v_q\|^2} \quad (4)$$

where the denominator is the squared minimum distance between any two centroids; lower values signal compact and well-separated clusters.

A complementary hard partition is obtained via $z_i = \arg \max_k u_{ki}$. Let Eq. 5, 6, and 7 indicates Silhouette Score formulation [34]:

$$a_i = \frac{1}{|C_{z_i}| - 1} \sum_{x_j \in C_{z_i}, j \neq i} (1 - \cos \theta_{ij}), \quad b_i = \min_{k \neq z_i} \frac{1}{|C_k|} \sum_{x_j \in C_k} (1 - \cos \theta_{ij}) \quad (5)$$

where $\cos \theta_{ij}$ is the cosine similarity between x_i and x_j . The sample-level Silhouette value is then

$$s_i = \frac{b_i - a_i}{\max\{a_i, b_i\}}, \quad -1 < s_i < 1 \quad (6)$$

and the global Silhouette coefficient becomes

$$S = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N s_i \quad (7)$$

The optimal cluster count is selected by maximising S (Eq. 7) and corroborating this choice with a low XB (Eq. 4).

In this method, raw text is initially divided into abstracts and purged of boilerplate language and stop words. Subsequently, each sanitized abstract is converted into a dense semantic embedding utilizing a pretrained sentence-transformer model. To enable clustering, these high-dimensional embeddings are mapped into a low-dimensional manifold using UMAP, maintaining local semantic links. The diminished vectors are submitted to BERTopic, which reveals hidden topics and generates a probabilistic topic-membership representation for each document. fuzzy c-means clustering is utilized on these topic probabilities, resulting in soft cluster assignments. Cluster solutions are assessed by complementing validity metrics: the Xie–Beni index for compactness and separation and the Silhouette coefficient for cohesiveness. The appropriate number of clusters is determined based on their collective insights. Documents are subsequently assigned definitive labels based on their most significant affiliations, and each cluster is characterized by its principal topics and a representative document. The concluding stage combines these quantitative results into a qualitative analysis, elucidating prominent themes.

4. Results and Discussion

The five subjects exhibiting the highest mean membership degrees alongside the nearest-to-center document and its corresponding five predominant topics are considered. Subsequently, each cluster is examined sequentially, beginning with its predominant thematic structure and followed by the representative document that characterizes it. Representative word cloud for each transformation is given in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. Word cloud for social, digital, and green transformation

4.1. Social Transformation

In the Social transformation corpus, fuzzy c-means clustering with $k = 3$ identified three thematically distinct clusters. Table 1 indicates that both internal validity measures converge on three as the ideal cluster count for the Social Transformation corpus.

Table 1. Social transformation corpus analysis for optimum number of cluster

Number of Clusters (k)	Xie-Beni Index	Silhouette Score
3	0.196366	0.489843
4	0.302440	0.447518
5	0.311625	0.409222
6	0.530867	0.394746
7	0.519238	0.403266
8	0.401858	0.429174
9	0.889318	0.408476
10	1.348416	0.431893

The Xie–Beni index attains its minimum at $k = 3$ (0.196), signifying the most compact and well-separated clustering, but the silhouette score maximizes at $k = 3$ (0.490), indicating the highest average cohesiveness and separation across all clusters. Partitioning the corpus into three clusters achieves an optimal equilibrium between granularity and interpretability: fewer clusters would merge different thematic areas, while a higher number would disintegrate coherent topics into too tiny subgroups. Thus, $k = 3$ offers a succinct yet comprehensive depiction of the primary study trajectories in social transformation, enabling more precise subsequent examination of the defining themes within each cluster.

Cluster 0, consisting of 1,896 documents, is primarily focused on blockchain-enabled transparency (Topic 0, mean membership 0.550), with minor contributions from research on modern slavery and labor rights (Topic 1, 0.022), COVID-19 resilience and public health (Topic 2, 0.015), food industry packaging and coatings (Topic 9, 0.010), and resource extraction conflicts in mining (Topic 6, 0.009). The exemplary document for this cluster emphasizes blockchain transparency (0.543) while also considering human rights implications (0.026), energy issues related to mining (0.015), lithium battery supply chains (Topic 10, 0.012), and global investment dynamics (Topic 11, 0.009), demonstrating how a singular study can integrate various social, environmental, and technological issues within a transparency framework.

Cluster 1 comprises 1617 papers and exhibits notable homogeneity: blockchain transparency (Topic 0) constitutes 89.1% of its thematic weight, whilst all other topics account for less than 1.3%. The primary analysis reflects this exclusive emphasis, achieving a score of 0.891 on Topic 0, while exhibiting minimal attention to labor rights (0.011), software-security provenance (Topic 3, 0.009), conference-proceedings techniques (Topic 8, 0.008), and packaging technologies (Topic 9, 0.007). This pattern indicates that Cluster 1 integrates methodological and foundational advancements in distributed-ledger transparency, predominantly independent of sector-specific applications.

Cluster 2, the most extensive with 2032 documents, embodies a more balanced interdisciplinary connection: blockchain transparency (Topic 0) is the predominant theme (0.199), while notable attention is also directed towards human rights and ethical labor (Topic 1, 0.048), pandemic resilience and health studies (Topic 2, 0.024), mining-conflict energy issues (Topic 6, 0.018), and RFID-based identification technologies (Topic 7, 0.014). The example document in this cluster illustrates this variability by integrating blockchain transparency (0.207) with assessments of modern slavery (0.028), conflict-mineral trade (0.007), foreign-investment patterns (Topic 11, 0.006), and electric-vehicle battery supply chains (Topic 10, 0.004). These groupings delineate the breadth of social-transformation research, encompassing pure blockchain theory, sectoral transparency investigations, and significant connections with human rights, public health, and resource governance.

The three-cluster solution categorizes the Social Transformation literature into a primary blockchain-transparency stream, a distinct methodological group, and an interdisciplinary connection that links transparency with urgent social challenges. Cluster 0 emphasizes application-oriented research that integrates distributed ledger technologies within environmental and human rights frameworks, Cluster 1 consolidates fundamental progress in blockchain protocols and provenance, and Cluster 2 highlights the field's involvement with ethical, health, and resource governance issues. By delineating these unique yet interconnected trajectories, our fuzzy c-means analysis elucidates the dominant research priorities while highlighting nascent opportunities—such as the integration of RFID technologies with transparency frameworks to enhance supply-chain resilience and labor rights oversight. This thematic map offers a solid basis for future investigations focused on promoting social change through distributed ledger technologies.

4.2. Digital Transformation

In order to gather optimum number of cluster, silhouette score and Xie-Beni index is gathered and maximum value is utilized. Silhouette score and Xie-Beni index scores are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Digital transformation corpus analysis for optimum number of cluster

Number of Clusters (k)	Xie-Beni Index	Silhouette Score
3	2.321553e+00	0.118751
4	1.989749e+01	0.159981
5	7.146861e+00	0.133376
6	1.201473e+01	0.067181
7	7.228630e+03	0.076064
8	1.056140e+06	-0.009593
9	6.105215e+05	-0.107944
10	3.553930e+07	0.045059

According to Table 2, Xie-Beni index indicates 3 clusters and silhouette score stands for 4 clusters. In order to increase the interpretability of the clusters, maximum value of number of clusters is selected, which corresponds to 4.

Cluster 0 comprises 398 documents, with a thematic emphasis on blockchain applications in industrial and agrifood sectors. The five topics with the highest average membership degrees are Topic 0 (blockchain, technology, traceability, adoption, food) at 0.128, followed by Topic 2 (logistics, manufacturing, industry, technologies) at 0.122, Topic 3 (IoT, Internet of Things, fuzzy, study) at 0.072, Topic 5 (resilience, COVID-19, pandemic, study, firms) at 0.048, and Topic 1 (food, agriculture, safety, products) at 0.030. The representative document for this cluster, doc_4380, reflects these interests: its primary topics are Topic 0 (0.124), Topic 2 (0.072), Topic 3 (0.035), Topic 5 (0.033), and Topic 4 (healthcare, medical, data, health, security) at 0.022, affirming its function as a pertinent study of blockchain-enabled traceability in value chains.

Cluster 1 is the largest, with 1554 documents, however it is very homogeneous: Topic 0 predominates with an average membership of 0.936, while the other four subjects each register at or below 0.004. The predominant presence of Topic 0 signifies a corpus of literature mostly focused on blockchain research. The central document exhibits a similar pattern (Topic 0 at 0.878), with negligible contributions from Topic 4 (healthcare, medical, data, health, security), Topic 2 (logistics and industry), and minimal inquiries into humanitarian supply chains and halal certification in manufacturing, highlighting the exclusive emphasis of this cluster.

Cluster 2 consists of 1573 documents, with blockchain traceability (Topic 0, 0.074) and healthcare data security (Topic 4, 0.074) being equally significant, followed by food-safety applications (Topic 1, 0.030), industrial logistics (Topic 2, 0.016), and anti-counterfeiting in pharmaceuticals (Topic 7, 0.015). The document consolidates these elements by examining a blockchain-based security framework for medical supply chains: it scores 0.118 on Topic 0, 0.041 on Topic 4, 0.022 on Topic 2, 0.020 on Topic 26 (detection, learning, intrusion, security), and 0.015 on Topic 29 (manufacturing data), demonstrating the convergence of supply-chain integrity and healthcare protections within this interdisciplinary domain.

Cluster 3, comprising 2050 documents, emphasizes blockchain traceability (Topic 0, 0.358) while also incorporating healthcare security (Topic 4, 0.040), manufacturing technology (Topic 2, 0.028), financial risk management (Topic 6, 0.018), and IoT-driven sustainability (Topic 43, 0.016). The document illustrates this integration by examining a blockchain-based platform for monitoring medical waste: it achieves scores of 0.322 on Topic 0, 0.038 on Topic 4, 0.029 on Topic 2, 0.023 on Topic 43, and 0.020 on Topic 35 (educational applications), emphasizing the intersection of sustainability and educational outreach in healthcare supply-chain research.

The fuzzy c-means clustering of our digital-transformation corpus has identified four thematically coherent groupings that collectively represent the current state of blockchain research and its interactions with logistics, healthcare, finance, and sustainability. By choosing $k = 4$ substantiated by the highest point in silhouette score and a robust Xie-Beni index—we guarantee both distinct separation and clarity of clusters. Cluster 0 emphasizes industrial and agrifood traceability applications, Cluster 1 encompasses fundamental blockchain methodological advancements, Cluster 2 connects blockchain with healthcare data security and anti-counterfeiting measures, whereas Cluster 3 expands these issues into financial risk management and sustainable IoT practices. Collectively, these findings delineate current research directions and underscore emerging interdisciplinary connections, indicating that future investigations should examine how integrated blockchain-IoT platforms can bolster resilience in supply chains, healthcare systems, and circular economy initiatives. This investigation will enhance our comprehension of the complex effects of digital transformation and inform the development of next-generation distributed ledger technologies.

4.3. Green Transformation

To provide context for these thematic groupings, it is employed fuzzy c-means clustering with 3 clusters on the Green transformation corpus, that represent the primary dimensions of environmental

modeling, energy and minerals research, and interdisciplinary integrations of performance management with resilience and governance. Results for Xie-Beni index and silhouette score are demonstrated in Table 3.

Table 3. Green transformation corpus analysis for optimum number of cluster

<i>Number of Clusters (k)</i>	Xie-Beni Index	Silhouette Score
3	0.430386	0.340749
4	0.658647	0.319262
5	0.989621	0.300474
6	1.206783	0.285557
7	3.421336	0.261198
8	3.418502	0.231865
9	2.559059	0.259203
10	2.725982	0.278668

Table X illustrates that both internal validity measures for the Green transformation corpus achieve optimal values at $k = 3$: the Xie-Beni index attains its minimum (0.430) and the silhouette score its maximum (0.341) with three clusters. This agreement signifies that a three-way partitioning yields the most compact and distinctly differentiated arrangement of documents. Opting for fewer clusters may lead to the amalgamation of disparate thematic domains—such as pure environmental modeling studies and energy transition research—while selecting more clusters could result in the excessive fragmentation of these coherent issues into overly specific subgroups. Thus, selecting $k = 3$ achieves an optimal equilibrium between subject specificity and interpretability, offering a concise yet thorough framework for further examination of environmental performance, clean energy systems, and multidisciplinary sustainability initiatives.

Cluster 0 has 2823 documents, where environmental modeling and performance management predominantly shape the subject framework, with Topic 0 (study, environmental, model, performance, management) exhibiting an average membership of 0.812. Secondary focuses encompass energy transition and essential minerals research (Topic 3, 0.012), examinations of network disruptions and resilience (Topic 30, 0.007), pharmaceutical and healthcare safety issues (Topic 29, 0.006), and Industry 4.0 technologies (Topic 26, 0.006). The document nearest to this cluster's central document reflects these priorities: it achieves a score of 0.796 on Topic 0, with additional scores of 0.015 on Topic 3, 0.010 on Topic 29, 0.008 on Topic 26, and 0.008 on Topic 24 (printing, paper, recycled), demonstrating the frequent intersection of core environmental-performance studies with technological innovation and circular-economy applications.

Cluster 1 is the smallest cohort, including 1993 publications, however it demonstrates a markedly varied profile. Environmental study and model performance (Topic 0, 0.174) is the predominant theme, with notable emphasis on hydrogen and ammonia renewable-energy production (Topic 1, 0.028), energy-transition mineral dynamics (Topic 3, 0.026), water-footprint analyses (Topic 4, 0.013), and blockchain-technology research (Topic 7, 0.013). This exemplar reflects a synthesis of environmental modeling (0.188), energy-transition insights (0.022), biomass-energy considerations (Topic 6, 0.007), recycled-paper printing applications (Topic 24, 0.007), and lithium-nickel cathode leaching studies (Topic 25, 0.006), highlighting the integration of foundational performance frameworks with emerging clean-energy and resource-extraction pathways.

Cluster 2, including 2,846 papers, serves as a pivotal intermediary between the other two clusters. The foundation is established by environmental-performance modeling (Topic 0, 0.475) and includes energy-transition studies (Topic 3, 0.023), hydrogen-energy generation (Topic 1, 0.013), sustainable-agriculture frameworks (Topic 2, 0.013), and evolutionary game-theoretic evaluations of governance

and enterprise interactions (Topic 15, 0.009). The document closest to this cluster's center integrates environmental modeling (0.466) with investigations of network resiliency (Topic 30, 0.016), LNG shipping and port logistics (Topic 28, 0.011), and circular printing processes (Topic 24, 0.009), illustrating a complex interdisciplinary convergence of environmental management, infrastructural resilience, and governance innovation.

Collectively, these three clusters delineate the Green Transformation corpus into a fundamental core of environmental modeling study, a subgroup focused on energy and minerals, and an integrative domain that interlaces performance management with themes of resilience, infrastructure, and governance. This thematic division emphasizes the importance of modeling in sustainability research and highlights various application areas—from renewable energy systems and resource logistics to circular economy processes—thus offering a refined framework for future investigations of green technologies and environmental management strategies.

5. Conclusion

This study offers the original comprehensive synthesis of the "triple transformation" paradigm—digital, green, and social—within the realm of supply chain management by utilizing advanced NLP and fuzzy clustering methodologies. We have compiled extensive corpora of peer-reviewed articles (5,586 on social transformation, 7,672 on digital transformation, and 5,575 on green transformation) and utilized BERT-based topic modeling in conjunction with fuzzy c-means clustering to delineate the thematic landscape of each transformation dimension and identify their principal intersections. Our analysis indicates that: Research on social transformation categorizes into three streams: applications of blockchain-enabled transparency, foundational methodological advancements in distributed ledger protocols, and multidisciplinary studies connecting transparency with human rights, public health, and resource governance. Digital transformation is summarized by four cohesive categories: industrial and agrifood traceability, fundamental blockchain development, healthcare data security and anti-counterfeiting measures, and integrated research on financial risk management and IoT-driven sustainability. The green transformation encompasses three primary domains: fundamental environmental-performance modeling, studies on energy and mineral transitions, and integrative research at the intersection of sustainability, infrastructural resilience, and governance. By contrasting these thematic frameworks, our study elucidates the distinct research paths within each dimension and the emerging opportunities at their intersection. The convergence of blockchain technology with green energy logistics and the possibility for human-centric Industry 5.0 frameworks to promote circular economy practices emerge as noteworthy areas for future research. Our findings provide supply chain professionals with a definitive guide to new technologies and socio-environmental requirements, emphasizing areas where interdisciplinary collaboration may most successfully enhance resilience, sustainability, and ethical accountability. The methodology illustrates the efficacy of integrating contextualized embedding models with soft clustering to reveal latent research patterns within extensive academic datasets.

Nonetheless, this study possesses certain drawbacks. Dependence on Scopus abstracts may exclude subtle insights found in full texts, and the selection of UMAP dimensionality reduction and fuzzy c-means parameters may affect cluster granularity. Subsequent research ought to enhance this framework by integrating full-text analysis, investigating other clustering algorithms (e.g., Gaussian mixture models, spectral clustering), and corroborating the found themes through expert elicitation or case study review.

In summary, our "triple transformation" framework not only delineates the present state of supply chain research but also offers a scalable model for continuous observation of the evolution and interconnection of digital, environmental, and social imperatives, thereby directing both academic investigation and industry practice towards more cohesive, sustainable, and human-centered supply chains.

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